

Reviewer 1

General:

Work is noble and interesting from the scientific viewpoint. The approach is well founded and the results are interesting. However, there are some issues that need to be considered before it is considered to be published. See my comments.

We appreciate all your comments. After a careful revision of the manuscript that considered your comments and those from others anonymous reviewers, we consider that this version has greatly improved. Listed below is a description of the major modifications we made to the manuscript.

- The final part of the “Abstract” has been modified in order to clarify some points mentioned by the reviewers.
- In the section “1. Introduction”, we have modified two paragraphs and defined the objective in a scientific way and more explicitly. We have also added a paragraph that describes the content of the article.
- We have reorganized and added subsections in section “3. Methods and data”:
 - 3.1. Model configuration
 - 3.2. Description and assessment of the experiments
 - 3.3. Observational data
 - 3.4. LULC dataset
 - 3.4.1 Changes of LULC
- A subsection on section “4. Results and discussion” was added to discuss the physical processes involved.
- Section “5. Conclusions” was modified at the suggestion of removing some sentences.
- The citation of some references was revised and modified.
- LULC's change matrix was added in supplemental material.
- We have checked the manuscript for errors in English language and style.

In the following we reply to comments and suggestions step by step.

Note: Line numbers refer to the original manuscript.

Major Comments:

1. *Results and Discussion: This section is too technically presented. Authors have said about the improvements only after using NALCMS, but they did not say anything about the science why it could be. Authors should show some scientific discussions e.g. page 12 line 7-8 analysing all or some of these variables in two simulations to understand the reason of improvement after using NALCMS.*

Response: We have improved the aforementioned section. The revised version of the manuscript adds a more detailed discussion.

2. *Page 11 line 14-17: I am concerned about the significance of these results. Did you perform any statistical test on this? Same comment applied for the wind speed and precipitation.*

Response: We appreciate the comment. We did not perform any significance test, however we did a statistical analysis and mentioned that reduction in errors' magnitude, which is very similar to those obtained by previous studies [1,42,49,50] where the three main variables are analyzed. We hope that this provides enough material to solve this issue.

Specific Comments:

1. *Page 1 line 27-28: “The results show... precipitation”. This statement is unclear. I did not find any sensitivity analysis on precipitation in this manuscript. Please rewrite it.*

Response: We have modified the statement in the revised version and we have rephrased the sentences from lines 23 to 29.

2. *Page 1 line 28-29: Compared to what? Please re-write this statement more explicitly.*

Response: Thanks for the comment, we re-wrote the statement as:

“Finally, when the NALCMS dataset was used, the most reliable weather forecast was observed between 48 and 72 hours.”

3. *Page 2 line 2: “[12] have shown....” Is it a proper way to write? Please check it. Authors have frequently used the citations in this way. Same comment applied to throughout the manuscript e.g.
Line 6: On the one hand, [13] studies
Line 13: On the other hand, [17] used the
Line 18: [16] and [18] have
Line 24: This work follows those [16] and [18] in the search
Page 3 line 15: ... out by [22].
Page 17 line 38: as that of [54] has shown*

Response: We appreciate the comment and we checked through the manuscript and modified it in the revised version.

4. *Page 2 line 23: Objective is not well defined. Authors should 4.*

Response: In the reviewed version we made the objective clearer. Actually, it has been changed as follows:

“The objective of this study is to evaluate the impacts of the use of different LULC data on simulated meteorological variables (wind speed at 10 m, near-surface temperature at 2 m and precipitation).”

5. *Page 2 line 25-32: These sentences are not the objective of this manuscript. This should go to the methodology section.*

Response: We agree with the referee and those lines should be in section 3. We removed them from the text and we added the following paragraph to the manuscript:

“The study area is described in section 2. The model configuration, the meteorological data, and LULC data are described in section 3. The results and discussion are presented in section 4, and conclusions are in section 5.”

6. *Page 2 line 11-12: Open bracket is not closed? something mistakes in this sentence.*

Response: Thanks for this observation, in the revised version we have corrected it.

7. *Page 8 line 8-10: Why didn't authors discuss it with a LULC change matrix?*

Response: The discussion on the land cover changes that are exposed in these lines refers to the changes that occurred in the meteorological stations. Considering the reviewer's comment, in the reviewed version the matrix is included in the supplementary material to provide this detail. Below, the change matrix that now is included in the supplementary material.

Table S1 LULC change matrix for USGS1993-NALCMS2005 (area in km²). Figure 3c shows in white the areas that changed (the elements off the diagonal of the matrix) while yellow represents the areas that did not show LULC changes (diagonal of the matrix).

Land cover class	1	2	3	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	13	14	15	16	18	19	21	24	Total NAL CMS
1-Urban and Built-Up Land	660	18	0	0	0	7	6	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	705
2-Dryland Cropland and Pasture	399	3,985	0	0	0	355	612	0	0	502	423	216	620	46	0	104	0	21	7,283
3-Irrigated Cropland and Pasture	39	985	0	0	0	160	340	0	0	594	0	2	5	10	0	0	0	0	2,135
5-Cropland/Grassland Mosaic	1	162	0	0	0	21	301	0	0	309	12	111	240	1	0	0	0	0	1,158
6-Cropland/Woodland Mosaic	0	1,701	0	0	0	0	182	0	0	531	284	118	1,225	0	0	0	0	0	4,041
7-Grassland	1,522	8,674	0	0	0	5,948	7,418	0	0	1,501	0	311	130	137	1	20	0	0	25,662
8-Shrubland	1,466	9,675	0	0	0	4,339	7,223	0	0	1,979	2	280	128	108	2	50	0	0	25,252
9-Mixed Shrubland/Grassland	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	7
10-Savanna	102	6,931	0	0	0	169	3,772	0	0	5,589	174	599	713	39	0	2	0	0	18,090
11-Deciduous Broadleaf Forest	6	143	0	0	0	18	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	171
13-Evergreen Broadleaf Forest	0	134	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	23	23	13	99	0	0	0	0	0	297
14-Evergreen Needleleaf Forest	122	2,805	0	0	0	741	1,856	0	0	2,555	1	108	178	22	0	1	0	0	8,389
15-Mixed Forest	67	6,982	0	0	0	253	6,000	0	0	2,472	426	5,895	7,594	40	0	32	0	2	29,763
16-Water Bodies	0	29	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	3	1	3	1	73	0	20	0	0	136
18-Wooded Wetland	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19-Barren or Sparsely Vegetated	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
21-Wooded Tundra	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
24-Snow or	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total USGS	4,388	42,224	0	0	0	12,011	27,722	0	0	16,058	1,346	7,670	10,936	476	3	233	0	23	123,090

8. Page 17 line 7-9: This is not the findings of this manuscript. This may be moved to results and discussion section.

Response: Thanks for the observation, we made the corresponding modification.